

INVESTIGATIONS OF PHENOLIC RESINS AS A MATRIX MATERIAL IN C-FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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INTRODUCTION

The phenol formaldehyde resins (PF resins, Phenoplasts) can be used as a matrix material for CFRPs (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics), C/Cs (Carbon /Carbon Composites) and C/C-SiC composites. Phenol can be derived as well from crude oil as from charcoal. The supply situation of PF resins therefore is stable; the relatively low costs and versatility of the resin properties allow widespread technological applications.

Charcoal and phenolic resins as solid polymers have some similarities concerning their structural changes which occur under thermal treatments like pyrolyses /1/. As a matter of fact, some basic structural properties of both, the charcoal and PF resin state, are transferred to their carbonised states whereas other polymeric properties discontinue and cause e. g. the macroscopical appearance /2/. The open and closed pores of carbonised charcoal and phenolic resins are such examples. This shows the need of chemical PF resin modifications and of precisely controlled curing processes but also the high potential to develop a deeper understanding.

A phenomenological model of processes leading to microstructural changes of carbon materials is applied and used as a guideline to modify raw materials and to perform the carbonisation process /3/. Subsequently the generated structures of the carbon materials derived from modified resins are inspected microscopically. The carbon structure and local molecular order is considered on the base of the findings of Oberlin /4/ on carbon materials. Parameters are changed, which influence the resin structure that is obtained after the carbonisation. Phenol formaldehyde resin synthesis is performed in order to explore these influences. The produced resins are subsequently used for the fabrication of composites. A correlation of the chemical state of the resin with macroscopic-mechanical (DMTA) and later with microstructural properties (optical microscopy; SEM; TEM) is aimed to be established. Therefore after the chemical resin modifications are made, CFRPs and C/Cs are produced under well controlled conditions using these resins. In this report the C/C state is generated in a pyrolysis experiment under inert gas atmosphere within the DMTA instrument's high temperature furnace. A reliable source of experimental mechanical data on fibre reinforced composites at all applied temperatures is the Dynamical Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) /5/. Therefore, DMTA-experiments are performed to reveal the impact of the chemical changes on the mechanical performance of the CFRP materials and their temperature dependence. To access the obtained microstructures Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) investigations are needed. For systematical investigations of the materials a powerful thin film preparation technique is indispensable. Such technique is the Focused Ion Beam based (FIB) technique. It is applied by the authors /6,7/ as a visually controlled and

pinpointed preparation and as an ion microscopical investigation method. The microporosity and microstructure of the thin film samples can be further investigated by SEM or TEM.

EXPERIMENTAL

The performed experiments include the in house chemical synthesis of phenolic resins, the fabrication of carbon fibre reinforced composites, the qualification of the DMTA-equipment for the planned experiments and the execution of mechanical and thermal tests within the pyrolysis processes under an inert gas atmosphere. The control of the obtained microstructures and in particular the porosity is done additionally.

Phenolic resins (basic resin E97783, produced by Dynea GmbH, Erkner, Germany) were modified in house by using the standard Schlenk technique. The water was removed under rough vacuum and at temperatures of about 45 °C. For the investigations of the influence of different solvents on the crosslinking process, different organic solvents like tetrahydrofuran, diethyl ether, ethyl acetate or furfuryl alcohol were added in a similar amount as the removed water. Furthermore tetrahydrofuran was also used as a solvent for resins that are chemically modified by tetraethoxy titanate or silicon alcoxides in order to influence the polymeric networking. After the modifying reaction finished, the volatiles (THF, alcohols) were removed under rough vacuum conditions to give the titanium and respectively silicon modified resins ready for infiltration

The carbon fibre reinforced polymer samples use the before mentioned resins and are produced in house. Their dimensions are approximately 100 mm x 25 mm x 3 mm and made by infiltrating stacks of carbon fibre cloths (0/90°) which were cut precisely out of well defined carbon fibre textiles (bundle size, weight per unit area, roughness etc.). The applied infiltration is a pure gravity infiltration of resin into preloaded stainless steel moulds. Curing takes place under pressure (max. 50 bar) and controlled time temperature profiles in an autoclave (PARR). The finished samples are sectioned into bending bars of 45 mm x 8 mm x 3 mm by a Struers Accutom saw with diamond blade.

For the subsequent Dynamical Mechanical Analysis (DMTA) the EPLEXOR 150N (GABO GmbH, Ahlden, Germany) equipment is used. It allows the acquisition of experimental data for the elastic modulus and for the internal damping ($\tan \delta$) in the temperature range of room temperature up to 1000 °C. The 3 point bending geometry is selected and based on a support with a 30 mm supporting length, rounded edges ($R = 2\text{mm}$) and also a rounded load piston. A high temperature furnace with an inert gas atmosphere option is used for the high temperature pyrolysis experiments. Supplementary to the Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) thermogravimetric (TG) investigations (Mod. STA 409, Netzsch GmbH) are performed.

The DMTA operation is based on the application of a periodical load σ and the measurement of the position (ϵ) which is also periodic and acts as the sample's answer. The time delay between both is expressed as a phase angle (δ), which resembles a mechanical damping (as $\tan \delta$). One component of the total load is static (zero is suppressed in Fig. 1) and the second component is a periodical force. The periodical force is of the sine type as sketched in Fig. 1. The multiple repeating of the mechanical loading and measuring process allows the evaluation (by a computer algorithm) of the phase angle (δ). This is done for each single DMTA data point separately. In practice the DMTA operation requires the secure fixation of a sample in its bending holder position by a small holding force (here 2 N). During the measurements this holding force is increased to the desired static force level. Superimposed to

the static load which serves as a parameter of the measurement, the dynamical, i. e. the periodic load, is applied to the sample and allows the derivation of the dynamical elastic modulus and the damping ($\tan \delta$). The specially designed high temperature bending assembly, the materials of the force axis (PM 1000) and the dedicated measurement engineering allow reliable mechanical investigation of thermal effects up to 1000 °C.

Fig. 1: Basic idea of Dynamical Mechanical Thermal Analysis: The phase shift between a forced periodic sine-load (σ) and the periodic position answer (ϵ) defines a phase angle δ in a temperature dependent way.

The referred work describes the influence of chemical modifications on phenolic resins by detecting the modifications' influence on the temperature dependence of the dynamical elastic modulus of carbon fibre reinforced phenolic resin matrices composites via thermal experiments performed by EPLEXOR 150N. The basic construction principle of the EPLEXOR 150N DMTA equipment is outlined schematically in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Schematic outline of the EPLEXOR 150N construction.

To confirm the high precision of the EPLEXOR 150N data acquisition on carbon fibre reinforced composites with a priori unknown mechanical properties is controlled in advance by investigating well known homogeneous materials as Titanium, Aluminium etc. which are characterised in literature and cover the range of expected stiffness.

The pure Titanium is a predestined mechanical reference material (elastic modulus at room temperature 100000 – 107000 MPa /8/) which furthermore is also suited as a temperature reference due to a structural phase transformation taking place at about 885 °C.

Bulk Titanium bars (grade 2) are cut gently by electrical discharge machining (EDM) into rectangular blocks of 2 mm x 8 mm x 45 mm size which show a very smooth surface (roughness less than 1 µm). This smooth surface reduces the level of detrimental interactions of the sample with the bending support assembly on the precision of the position and damping measurements. The experiments on Titanium samples are performed under a fixed static load and variable temperatures. The results (Fig. 3) show the expected literature value of the E-Modulus for pure Titanium at room temperature and additionally the expected low damping (tan δ)-values in the range of some 10^{-3} . The observed damping is sensitive to the detailed shape of the support (shape of the support's edges, dry or greased environment, smooth or rough structured interacting surfaces). The damping is regarded as being most representative for the test sample bulk material if rounded edges and smooth surfaces are in interaction with the test sample. The reliability of the temperature measurement inside the furnace is also experimentally proven (Fig. 3). The known α/β -phase transformation of Titanium (α phase at low, β phase at high temperature) takes place at about 885°C and is accompanied by changed binding conditions between the hexagonal (α)- and bcc (β)-crystal systems. The EPLEXOR 150N system proved sufficiently sensitive to reveal the effect of the changed mechanical behaviour in the hexagonal and bcc Titanium phase by the 3 point bending experiments at the transformation temperature. Additionally the efficiency of the inert gas protection of the reactive Titanium material is proven under nitrogen gas streams of at least 250 l/min. Any decrease of the high temperature stiffness above the transformation temperature due to oxidation effects are excluded. This experiment could be repeated several times with the same sample and was leading to identical results.

The experiments on homogeneous reference materials as Titanium substantiate the reliability of the testing method and confirm the reproducibility of the EPLEXOR 150N equipment in practical operations on other classes of materials like carbon fibre reinforced composites whose properties are less well known in advance.

Fig. 3: Control of EPLEXOR 150N performance based on Titanium as reference material

The DMTA experiments performed on carbon fibre reinforced polymeric matrix composites with different matrices are supplemented by thermogravimetical (TG) and microscopical experiments obtained from the same matrix and composite materials. All matrices investigated here are based on the same base resin E 97783 (Dynea, Erkner/Germany); they are modified chemically within the Technical University of Chemnitz.

RESULTS

DMTA measurements obtained from composites and TG analyses gained on matrix resins can reveal interesting informations about the chemical processes taking place at elevated temperatures when being combined.

DMTA and TG-results gained from composites using the resin E 97783 are compiled in Fig. 4. In the range of 100 - 180°C reaction products of the pursuing polycondensation reactions like water and formaldehyde are still released. The relative mass losses are larger than the reductions in stiffness (E-Modulus). This indicates the activation of inherent strengthening mechanisms during curing. The formation of new dimethylene ether and additional methylene bridges can be regarded as a chemical reason. Also the conversion of dimethylene ether units into the thermodynamically more stable CH₂-bridges takes already place /3/. The mass losses are almost negligible up to 350 °C but DMTA reveals a significant weakening of the matrix above about 270 °C under otherwise minor structural changes in the material. Above 350 °C the thermal degradation of the phenolic resin becomes essential. The process of resin hardening is, specially at elevated temperatures, a not abruptly terminating process but consists of processes of cracking less stable bonds and generating other more stable bonds as methylene bridges, instead. However a large number of aromatic compounds like toluene and m-xylene but also methane and carbon oxides are released in this temperature range /9/. But,

Fig. 4: Base resin E 97783 under thermal investigation by DMTA and TG.

even large mass losses are taking place, the matrix activates mechanisms to regain the stiffness. I. e. the distribution of bridge types changes in favour of more stable ones which compensate the macroscopical weakening effects which accompany the obviously increasing porosity. New network formation causes the stiffness of the material. In the following temperature range of carbonisation (above 500 °C) the continuing mass losses (end chains, hydrogen) increase the porosity which result in an uncompensated loss in stiffness until at even higher temperatures stiff carbon structures (polyaromatic network) take over the load. This phenomenological explanation shows the availability of chemical mechanisms whereas their final prove is a future task.

The effect of chemical modifications of the base resin and the investigation of their influences on the macroscopical mechanical performance is considered now. Therefore a series of syntheses is performed supplying resins with simple substitutions of the solvent (water) of the E 97783 resin. The composites made of these resins show that even simple resin modifications already can be revealed by analysing the thermal mechanical behaviour in DMTA experiments (Fig. 5).

Fig.5: The effect of solvent substitution on the mechanical stiffness (Base resin E 97783)

All different resins derived from the same base resin (E 97783) retain inherently some basic characteristics (Fig. 5) as e. g. matrix weakening at around 350 °C: At the same time the morphological effect (porosity) was varied by resin modification and could be reduced as seen at about 550 °C. The closed porosity of the composites was reduced from about 10% to less than 2% (Fig.6) as the also performed microscopical analyses revealed.

Syntheses and mechanical investigations of phenolic resins derived from the same base resin (E 97783) but under the action of essentially changed curing mechanisms (titanium modified) are performed next and show a distinctly changed temperature characteristics compared to the other resins derived from the same base (Fig. 7). It is easily seen that from the beginning of the thermal treatment at a temperature of about 120 °C differing networking conditions and therefore changed temperature dependences are effective. The bridges and mixtures of bridges at lower temperature reorganize during the thermal treatment and change for a more and more thermally stable polymeric network structure.

Fig. 6 Reduction of closed porosity for solvent substituted resins

Fig. 7: Temperature characteristics of a titanium modified E 97783 base resin

As a conclusion, DMTA proves to be a very well suited and powerful technique to control and objectify the mechanical properties of phenolic resins. Comparing the results gained from various resins which were subjected to modifications (from simple solvent substitution to catalytically induced network modifications) but always derived from the same base resin (E 97783), distinct differences are found by macroscopic phenomenological DMTA analyses.

Supplementary to the DMTA and TG investigations it is desired to generate a visual impression of the matrix constitution within the fabricated carbon fibre reinforced composites. Therefore a pinpointed resin area between adjacent Carbon Fibres is prepared by the Focused Ion Beam Lift-Out technique [6,7] and imaged by conventional Transmission Electron Microscopy (Fig. 8). The FIB technique is extraordinarily well suited for the preparation of thin films from very heterogeneous or cracked materials, due to the relatively small level of

artefacts induced to the sample by this method. Fig. 8 shows a randomly selected region of a C/C composite located between three carbon fibres (type: T800) filled with E97783 resin. The fine porosity (25 nm – 100nm) is easily recognized but the influencing parameters are difficult to identify and to control. Depending on the C-fibre functionality (here the C-fibres are desized by heating in vacuum) a more or less pronounced accumulation of closed porosity near fibres can be observed quite often. Other regions of increased closed porosity are preferentially located near open pores, which serve as degassing channels during pyrolysis.

Fig. 8 Matrix rich region (E 97783) between Carbon fibres

CONCLUSION

The selection of solvents is an important parameter to change the resin's viscosity and also to control the macroscopical porosity of the CFRP material. The hardening behaviour and in particular the generated porosity determine the suitability of a resin for a subsequent carbonisation. Already existing porosity in the CFRP state is not redeveloping. The porosity on the microscopic scale, the kind of network which is forming and the thermal stability can be influenced substantially by controlling the polymerisation conditions via the raw materials condition and by adequate thermal processing. The thermal mechanical loading (DMTA) under inert gas atmosphere (N₂, Ar) allows to detect structural changes that affect the mechanical properties even at high temperatures up to 1000 °C. The presence of oxygen above 600°C would decrease the stiffness steadily.

The Dynamical Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) reveals the changes in the polymeric state from temperatures below 150°C up to 1000 °C in a reliable way. Structural changes of phenolic resin matrices which are influencing the mechanical properties (E-Modulus, damping (tan δ)) significantly take place only within the temperature range from 150°C to 600°C. The constancy of the Elastic Modulus and damping at temperatures above 600°C is achieved when supplying a sufficient intensive inert gas stream. The DMTA analysis is able to discriminate chemical changes of the resins from a macroscopical mechanical level. The identification of the active bridging mechanisms within the polymeric network is not possible. But DMTA is able to acquire the precise temperature dependences of the mechanical properties of any resins. The availability of pure standard samples with well known binding

and networking mechanisms and transformation temperatures would help to understand the usually occurring mixed binding situations and to identify their pure components together with their relative importance under thermally varying conditions.

A supplementing microstructural analysis is very desirable but has to act on nano scale (e. g. matrix porosity) which makes its realization costly and difficult to realize. The Focused Ion Beam thin film preparation technique at least has the technological potential to access the nanostructure for imaging it by SEM and TEM investigations in a very profound way. On this experimental base systematical investigations of the parameters inducing and controlling micro- and nanoporosity are very promising and may lead to a better understanding of the reactions occurring under thermal loading, which is one more step to understand the mechanical properties of the carbon fibre reinforced composites on a microscopic base.

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